

Lexical-Semantics processes of turkish origin in the albanian lexicon

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The lexicon of the Albanian language has changed during the history of the development of this language. It is constantly enriched with words, especially with new meanings, which have reflected the life of the people but also argued the development of Albanian, in the face of linguistic globalization.

The lexicon of the Albanian language is known as an autochthonous lexical fund and the other as a borrowed fund, of course, as a lexicon that has come during different periods and not all at once.

The words of the Albanian language are words that the Albanian language has inherited from the Illyrian. They are of Indo-European origin, of a pre-Illyrian phase of the language or words created during the evolution of Illyrian and Albanian. Indo-European source words are more easily distinguished by comparison with the corresponding words of Indo-European languages close to the Albanian language.(Naser Pajaziti, 2019, p. 153).

Words formed from inherited Indo-European words are “temporal”- alb. *kohor*, “paternal”-alb. *atëror*, “nomadic”- alb. *shtegtar*, “vinedresser”-alb. *vreshtar*. Later formations are “thunder”-alb. *bubullin*, “whistle”-alb. *fëshfërin*, “whisper”-alb. *pëshpërit*, “knock” –alb. *trokas* and “gurgle”- alb. *gurgullon*.

In terms of borrowing, it is considered that the borrowed word is most often entered with the item, object, or phenomenon. There have been cases when borrowings have entered even when Albanian has had its say, for special linguistic styles, e.g. “I abuse”-alb. *Abuzoj*, “experiment” – alb. *eksperimentoj*, alongside the words “abuse”-alb. *shpërdoroj*, “try”-alb. *provoj*, “notice”-alb. *vërej*.

Language establishes relationships between different generations; it transmits the whole collective perception from one generation to the next, thus ensuring the social continuity of a community. Despite technological developments (which are recent) to prove oral heritage, written language remains the best means of transmitting human experience from generation to generation.

The lexical richness of the Albanian language is grouped according to semantic connections and according to origin.

The words of the Albanian language are grouped according to semantic connections:

- 37 - With the same meaning – Synonyms
- 38 - In the opposite sense – Antonyms
- 39 - With different meanings - Homonyms.

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41 **KEYWORDS:** Homonyms, synonyms, antonyms, types of lexical-semantic processes, foreign
42 words, negative antonyms.

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44 *1. Introduction*

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46 Most of the Turkish lexical words had direct input from Turkish, some of them
47 penetrated into Albanian through other languages in contact with Albanian and mainly through
48 Serbo-Croatian and Bosnian (which derive from the same linguistic branch). However, the
49 intellectual class of the society tried to adhere to the standardization of Albanian and avoided as
50 much as possible the use of the lexical fund originating from Turkish. The rest of the educated,
51 especially those who had had the opportunity to be educated in the east, continued the linguistic
52 use of these words.

53 Lexical-semantic processes are: (Vajzović, 1999), (Polysemy is a sign that has many meanings,
54 but with the same etymology, expresses the same content; Homonymy is a sign that has two
55 meanings, with different etymologies; Synonymy represents many signs with the same meaning,
56 with the same or close semantic value and Antonyms represents different signs with semantic
57 contradictions. Polysemy manifests as a correlation between old meaning and new, motivated by
58 meaning changes or derivative possibilities.

59 Turkish words came to Albanian, in two ways:

- 60 1. At the time when the two languages had linguistic contacts
- 61 2. At a time when the two languages had no linguistic contact. course, the whole thing was
62 governed by politics and the general situation in the Balkan region.

63 The giver to the recipient must always be considered.

64 Albanian words derived from other languages must definitely adapt to the linguistic and
65 grammatical rules of the receiving language.

66 The following language transmissions are known in the Albanian language:

- 67 1. The same model from Turkish to Albanian
68 2. A part of the word from Turkish to Albanian is identical, but we have an internal difference,
69 especially during the articulation of the word
70 3. Free transformation, when the sounds from the input model to the receiving model change
71 completely.

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73 2. *Lexical-semantics processes in the Albanian language*

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75 The birth of synonymy in the Albanian language, as well as other phenomena, is
76 directly related to the development and constant change of the language (Pajaziti, 2019).

77 Synonyms are words that are different in sound composition and origin, but close to or the same
78 in meaning. They serve to distinguish semantic or stylistic nuances. In the Albanian language,
79 synonyms can be named, such as “Girl”-alb. *Vajzë-gocë-cucë*, “initiative”-alb. *nismë*; adjectives:
80 “Current/actual - present-day – present” / alb. *aktual – i sotëm- i kohës – prezent*; verb: “I notice
81 - I look - I see - I observe” / alb. *Vërej – shikoj – shoh – vrojtoj*; adverbs: “suddenly” – alb.
82 *papritmas – befas – papritur*; conjunctions: “and” – alb. *e – edhe – dhe*. (Pajaziti, pp. 149-150).

83 Lexical-semantics processes are: Polysemy, Homonymy, Synonymy and Antonym
84 (Vajzoviç, 1999).

85 Homonyms - They are words with the same sound composition and different meanings. They
86 have arisen from the changes that have taken place in the language during its historical
87 development. Thus, different words in different stages of the development of the Albanian
88 language have been matched by the phonetic composition or by the pronunciation, while they
89 have remained different in meaning. In addition to phonetic matching, homonyms have also
90 arisen from the dissolution of polysemy. For example, alb. *verë/stinë* and *verë/pije*; “wine /
91 season and wine / drink”; alb. *çikë/copë e vogël: çikë/vajzë: çikë/Zog i vogël shtegtar*: “pinch /
92 small piece: pinch/girl: pinch / small migratory bird”. (Naser Pajaziti, 2019, p. 152).

93 Homonyms in the Albanian language are divided into two groups: full homonyms and partial
94 homonyms. Complete homonyms are words that belong to the same lexical-grammatical
95 category, sound the same, but have completely different lexical meanings, e.g. verb: “bake”-alb.
96 *pjek* / “put on fire” – alb. *vë në zjarr* and “bake” – alb. *pjek* / “meet” – alb. *takoj*.

97 Partial homonyms are words with different lexical-grammatical categories that belong to
98 different parts of speech and partially coincide with each other. Partial homonyms appear in
99 special word forms during writing or pronunciation. Homophormes appear when special
100 grammatical forms of different words match during pronunciation and during their writing, such
101 as “wear”-alb. *vesh* (verb) and “ear”-alb. *vesh* (noun), “catch” – alb. *Zë* (verb) and “voice” – alb.
102 *Zë* (noun). (Gjuha shqipe 1, 2019, p. 152).

103 Homographs are words that match only during the writing and are distinguished by different
104 accents, such as “ornament” – alb. *stoli* / “seat” – alb. *ulëse* and “ornament”- alb. *stoli* and
105 “accessory”- alb. *stoli-assessor*. Homophones are words that match only in pronunciation, but
106 that are written differently, such as “loop”-alb. *lak* (in dialectal discourse - meaning of alb. *lak* is
107 Brother), while “loop”- alb. *lak*: “knot in the rope”. (Naser Pajaziti, 2019).

108 In homonyms, there is no connection between the markers, written and the same pronounced.
109 E.g.: “Orphan”-alb. *Jetim* / without family – alb. *pa familje*, “naive in the figurative sense”. (Ibid.
110 p. 181). Homonymy is usually derived from polysemy. We have polysemy when the form of the
111 word suggests different meanings, but all those meanings are related according to the semantic
112 line. (Hudson, 2000).

113 Polysemy has many meanings:

114 “Not worth: free, in vain” / alb. *Badihava: pa pagesë, kot*

115 “Blessings-wealth, fertility” / alb. *Bereqet-pasuri, plleshmëri*

116 “Worry, passion” / alb. *Merak-brengë, passion*

117 “Shopping, trade” / *Pazar-blerje*, “treat commodity-wealth” / alb. *Mall-pasuri*; while this in
118 Albanian also appears as a homonym: “longing” - alb. *Mallëngjim*.

119 Homonyms are: “money”-alb. *para, sofa* – alb. *divan* (Vajzoviç, 1999) “still, yet” (ar. Hala,
120 halen), but alb. *halla* – tr. “Hala” – “Aunt”. (Dizdari, 2006).

121 “Sebep” in alb.-*cause* in Turkish, which changes meaning in the Albanian language, family. The
122 Turkish word “Tr.mal”-alb. *Mall* / Eng. “Commodity/wealth and longing” create homonymy in
123 the Albanian language, but in both cases, it comes with the root of Turkish.

124 There are some words that make homonyms with Albanian words, such as alb. *Çaj-pije* / “to
125 crush something, to divide and tea (drink)”; *Ocak*, tr. / alb. *Oxhak*-“Chimney” - the place where
126 the smoke comes out on the roof and in Albanian is the hearth of the house, except the meaning
127 conveyed by Turkish; “button-stamp” (alb. *pullë-kopsë*), “postage stamp” – alb. *markë postare*,
128 (Hoxha, 2015) “Scorpio”: alb. *Akrepi* – *Scorpio*, (Insect, Scorpio, Horoscope sign).

129 “Sofa” – alb. *divan*, *minder*, *presidium* / Grand Assembly created by statesmen, (Neziri,
130 2006:236), background with more visible views among the crowd of people.

131 “Housing rent and candles” (in alb. *Qira* / tr. *Kira*), both of which came through Turkish

132 “Halka – metal circle”, alb. *Halka*, “Chain, handcuffs, circle earrings”.

133 “Leğen” – alb. *Legen*, “Basin, metal or plastic container for water and human skeleton”

134 “Talaz” – “wave”, alb. *Tallaz*-“Sea waves”

135 Qualitative expressions for people who are still used are alb. *batal*-“led down, not righteous,
136 stupid-taken” (Vajzović, 1999). Of course, such qualities are used within the context of
137 antonyms, alongside words with a positive (mejorative) meaning.

138 Synonyms are spelled and pronounced differently while naming the same thing. E.g.: “paint-
139 color is not getting paint / has no character” / alb. *boja- ngjyra*, *s’po merr bojë/s’ka karakter*;
140 *sahat-orë*; *komshi-fqinjë*; “o’clock-hour /alb.*sahat-orë*; neighbors” / alb. *komshi-fqinjë*; Whereas,
141 the word Samar does not have any correspondents in Albanian but comes with the meaning of
142 the load on the back. Other synonyms are “guest house” – alb. *konak-shtëpi*, “dead-end street” –
143 alb. *qorrsokak-rrugë pa dalje*.

144 Genuine synonyms are common in every use of them: e.g. “Head” – alb. *Kokë* – *krye*, “pencil:-
145 “pen”-alb. *laps-kalem*, “change – difference”- alb. *ndyshim* – *diferencë*, “doctor” – alb.*Doktor* –
146 *heqim* – *mjek*, “understand” –alb. *kuptoj* – *Marr vesh*. Partial synonyms are words that are
147 synonymous with certain uses. E.g.: “Family – door”/alb. *Familje* – *derë*. (Pajaziti, 2019).

148 Synonyms are: “Friend:dost-jaran”-alb.*mik*; “time: vakt-zaman”-alb. *kohë*; “trust”:*din-iman*;
149 “talisman”- *hajmali-talisman*; “mahogany”- *sini-sofër*; “sofa”- *minder-divan-kanape*. (Ibid, pp.
150 196). Existing synonyms along with the words of the Albanian language are: *bajrak-flamur*-

151 “flag”, *bela-telashe*-“trouble”, *dugme-pullë*-“stamp”, *hava-qiell*-“sky”; *havaja-moti*-“weather” /
152 in folk. Synonyms that are seldom used are: “window”-alb.*dritare* /*tr.penxhere*, *kapi-dera*-
153 “door”, *xhenet-parajsa*-“paradise”, *zor-vështirë*-“hard”; *Shejtan* / *nalet* / *djall*-“demon”, in
154 Albanian preserves the mentioned synonymous meanings / in fact colloquial Albanian has the
155 same meaning *shejtan* / *nalet*; “Evil / thief” / *Harami*, *i keqi*, *hajdut*, *hërsëz*; *Kuvet* / *takat-force* /
156 *Kuvet/takat-forcë*- “strength”; *Vase* / *pot* / *vazo:saksi*; *gajle* / “dert-worries”.

157 Synonym: *tr. And alb. mahsuz-kastile-nergut*, “in particular, exactly” (Hoxha, 2015);
158 *peshqesh/hedie/dhuratë* / “gift”; *qebe/batanije* / “blanket”; *çamçakëz/sakëz-gomë përtypëse* /
159 “chewing gum”.

160 The days of the week, the months, used with the same names and which in the Albanian
161 language turned out like this: *Sali-e martë* –“Tuesday”: transferred in the Albanian language as
162 the male name *Sali*, even *Salih*; “Sunday”, *tr. Pazar-market*, homonymous alb.*Treg/ Pazar* –
163 “market”/ *Pazar*. Then, the month *Ocak*, *tr. - January*, in alb. *Oxhak*-“chimney” homonym,
164 *kasım* – “November”: masculine noun *Kasem*. (Turqishtja e re, 2007).

165 Turkish words - synonyms along with Albanian words: *bajagi-goxha* / “enough”, *bakshish*,
166 *tr.hedie-alb.dhuratë* / “gift”, *tr.bajrak-alb.flamur* / “flag”, *tr.barut-alb.eksploziv* / “explosive”,
167 *tr.beşik* / *alb.beshik*-“cradle”, *tr.bezi-alb.material* / “cloth”; *tr.boya* / *alb.bojë* / “paint”,
168 *tr.budalla-alb.i marrë* / “mad”; (*Balkanism*) *çoban-bari* / “shepherd”, *tr.çorba-alb.* does not
169 mean like soup in Turkish, *tr. cebe*, *alb.qebe-batanije* / “blanket”; *tr.torba-tr.çanta-alb.çantë* /
170 *bag*-similar are stored in Albanian; *tr. köşe* / *qoshe*-“angle”, *tr. adaş* / *alb. adash*-“peer or of the
171 same name”, *tr. avaz-alb. zë* / conversational Albanian keeps it for habit (*avaz* “same” = “same
172 habit”); *byrazer-brother* (used with negative connotation), *quarter-15 minutes*, *tr. book* / *qitap*-
173 “book of religion”, *tr.dakika-alb.minuta* “minutes”.

174 Antonyms - They are words with different sound compositions and opposite meanings, such as
175 “winter-summer”/alb. *dimër-verë*, “night-day”/ alb.*natë-ditë*, “black-white”/alb. *I zi-I bardhë*,
176 “bottom-up”/alb. *poshtë-lart*. Within the antonym pair, words are subject to opposition,
177 complementing each other. (Naser Pajaziti, 2019, p. 151).

178 Antonyms are classified according to their semantic opposition and construction. Antonyms
179 according to semantic opposition are distinguished into full antonyms and partial antonyms.

180 Complete antonyms are words with completely opposite meanings. They are opposed in the
181 basic sense or in most meanings, e.g.: “good-bad”/alb.*mirë-keq*, “love-hate”/alb. *dashuri-*
182 *urrejtje*. Partial antonyms represent contradictions in some of their meanings. They are fewer
183 than the antonyms of the first group. For example, “Clean-Dirty”/alb. *I pastër-I papastër*,
184 “Registered-Unregistered”/alb.*I regjistruar-i paregjistruar*.

185 Antonyms according to the structure are divided into antonyms with completely different
186 structures and with partially the same structure. Antonyms with completely different structures
187 are prepositions or words derived without any connection between them.

188 The only connection between these antonyms is the semantic one. For example, “son-
189 daughter”/alb. *djalë-vajzë*, “sister-brother”/alb.*motër-vëlla*, “Young – old”/alb.*I ri – I vjetër*.

190 Antonyms with partly the same structure are words that are related to each other by origin. For
191 example, “unblock-block”/ *zhbllokoj-blllokoj*, “legal-illegal”/alb. *legal-ilegal*, “Tired-
192 Tireless”/alb. *I lodhur-I palodhur*. (Naser Pajaziti, 2019, p. 152).

193 Antonyms are: *sabah/aksham/eng.* morning/night; *bajat-taze/eng.* stale-fresh; *dost-dushman/eng.*
194 “Friend-enemy”, *xhehenem-xhenet/eng.* “hell-paradise”, *tr. şeytan / alb.shejtan-*
195 *tr.melek/alb.meleqe/eng.*”Devil/angel”; *tr.hak/tr.hile/eng.* “right”/tr. “cheat”; *tr. kolay/kollaj –*
196 *zor/eng.*.. “easy/ hard”.

197 Words that do not change in Albanian and have no correspondents in Albanian are
198 *Deve/eng.*”camel”, *tr. Durbi-alb. Dylbi/eng.* “Binoculars”, *Duhan/eng.* “tobacco”, *düşek-*
199 *dyshek/eng.* “mattress”, *düşeme-dysheme/eng.* “Floor”, *çay-çaj/eng.* “tea”, *çorapa-çorapë/eng.*
200 “socks”, *çekiç/eng.* “hammer”, *çelik/eng.* “steel”, *çizme/eng.* “boots”, *fincan-filxhan/eng.*”cup”,
201 *yorgan-jorgan/eng.* “quilt”, *yastik-jastëk/eng.* “pillow”, *kafaz/eng.cage, pambuk/eng.* “Cotton”,
202 *sabun-sapun/eng.*” Soap”, *cam-xham/eng.* “glass”, *cami-xhamia/eng.* “mosque”, *cep-xhep/eng.*
203 “pocke”t.

204 Words that present professionalism, historicism, localism, archaism, etc., are: *agë/*”lord”, *beg/*
205 “gentleman”, *xhevap/*”answer”, *xhami/*”mosque”, *filxhan/* “cup”, *sarma/* “wrapping”, *sevdalli/*
206 “lover”. (Vajzoviç, 1999).

207 *Bayram-Festa e Bajramit*/eng. “Eid Holiday”, *şeker-sheqer/bonbone*/eng. “sugar-candy”,
208 *harçlık-harxhi/shpenzimet*/eng.”expenses”.

209 *Ortak*,/eng. “Partner”, coming from *Orta, tr.* the middle and means someone with whom he
210 shares a property or joint work,” partner / co-owner”. (Turqishtja e re, 2007).

211 Regarding semantic adaptation, there are two: lexicon-semantic transmission and stylistic-
212 semantic transmission. In the lexical-semantic concept, from the recipient's language to the
213 recipient, we have a new meaning, in fact the word comes with a different meaning, or the label
214 has existed earlier in the receiving language, but changes the content.. (Vajzoviç, 1999).

215 Semantic transmissions in our language have been, as partial semantic adaptations and complete
216 semantic adaptations.

217 1. Partial semantic adaptations are:

218 *Bahçe*-“garden, a meadow with fruits and vegetables”; al. *Bahçe* /conversational bashçe

219 *Çar*-“profit, undeserved”; al. *çar*

220 *Haram*-“ill-gotten gain, hurt, the wrong one, prodigal son”; al. *haram*

221 *Muhabet*-“friendly conversation, chat, love relationship”; al. *muhabet*

222 *Turşu*-“Pickled canned vegetables, stored things”; al. *turshi*

223 *Zanat*-“Craft, interest in something, art skills for something”; al. *zanati*

224 *Marifetlik*-“mastery, politeness”; al. *marifetllëk* (conversational)

225 *Vesvese*-“suspicion, depression”; al. *vesvese* (mainly on attitude of being clean).

226 *Zeytin*-“oil from olive, in Turkish it makes sense to olive, while in Albanian it makes
227 sense of oil”; al. *zejtin* (conversational)

228 *Behar*-“greenery, spring blossom”; al. *Behar*

229 *Cumbuz*- “fun, too many people making noisy”; al. *xhumbuz* (conversational)

- 230 2. Complete semantic adaptations
- 231 *Bardak* – “Drinking bowl, glass”; al. *bardak* (conversational)
- 232 *Bakşış* – “gift, a small reward for any work”; al. *bakshish* (conversational)
- 233 *Çanak* – “wooden dishes”; al. *çanak*
- 234 *Basma/ basëm* alb. – “type of material, from Turkish prints”; here the meaning is changed
- 235 into material for clothes.
- 236 *Yapı* – “home or building”; al. *japia* (conversational)
- 237 *Bahane / behane* – “error, flaw, incompletely”; al. *behane* (conversational)
- 238 *Parmak* – “the fence of the wood or of the iron to the door or window”; al. *parmaku*
- 239 *Bayat* – “not fresh, old”; al. *bajate* (conversational)
- 240 *Merak* – “concern, worry, passion”; al. *Meraki* (folk and conversational)
- 241 *Mangup* – “free politician, hunter, unemployed”; (conversational) al. *mangupi* (Vajzoviç,
- 242 f. 177-178).

243 Turkism also represents a very rich borrowing fund, both in Albanian and in other Balkan

244 languages. In the layer of these borrowings, it is emphasized that there are words that are not

245 Turkish sources, such as Persian ones, but which have penetrated through the Turkish language.

246 Turkish borrowings have included all the layers of the lexicon of material and mental life, where

247 these traces are deeper in religious life, housing and culinary habits, doctrines, customs, and

248 popular beliefs in general, while the weakest appear in the field of livestock and agriculture, in

249 the names of plants and animals. (IAP, 1989).

250 At the time when Albanian was formed as a written language, that is, in the ancient period,

251 Greek borrowings and Latin borrowings are present. These borrowings have come from

252 numerous contacts between people. Such are: *kishë/* “church”, *prift/* “priest”, *fëmijë/* “child”,

253 *mashkull/* “male”, *mik/* “friend”, *shok/* “friend”, *luan/* “lion”, *pulë/* “chicken”, *qen/* “dog”, *kaproll/*

254 “roe dee”, *shtëpi/* house, *portë/* “gate”, *pyll/* forest, *pemë/* “tree”, *pjeshkë/* peach, *ulli/* “olive”,

255 *këngë/* “song”, *mëkat/* “sin”, *I varfër/* “Poor”, *verdhë/* “yellow”, *ftoj/* “invite”, *mbroj/* “protect”,

256 *shërbej/* “serve”. (Naser Pajaziti, 2019, p. 155).

257 The stylistic-semantic transmission can be analyzed in the examples of Turkish words in folk

258 literature/dialectology, (Asllani, 1963)

259 *Halla, shakaxhiu, xhan, dervisha, xhepe.* // “Auntie, joker, baby/spirit, dervish”-member of a
260 Muslim sect, pocket. (Asllani, 1963).

261 Words of Turkish origin encountered in folk literature, argues that their presence is more
262 pronounced in folk literature than in modern literature, but this does not mean that they are not
263 yet present in our language today. Like: al. *esëll*-on “an empty stomach”, al. *amanet*-“behest”,
264 *testament* “last will”. (Çeta, 1974), then al. *Kurban*-“sacrifice”, al. *izë me m’dhanë*-“to give
265 permission”, al. *Hala*-“still, yet”. We cannot say that for five centuries, only Turkey had an
266 impact on the human existence and linguistic fundament of Albanians in these lands, but even
267 the people had an impact on the Turkish language. Such are the words: al. *Boza*-“fresh juice”, al.
268 *ulluk*-“spout”, (Çabej, 1976, p. 74), “food”: al. *tava me mish*-“meat pancakes”, al. *gjella me*
269 *mushkëri*-“liver food”. Some of the Turkish words present in the Albanian language, thanks to
270 the earliest entry into Albanian, are already in Albanian and somehow have been adopted by the
271 Albanian language because they are irreplaceable with an expression of the Albanian source.
272 Such words are: al. *fital*-“wick”, al. *kapak*-“cap”, al. *kukull*-“doll”, *qese*-“bag”. (Gjevori, 1968,
273 pp. 98-312). Turkish words have been found in the literary and popular use of Albanian, early,
274 but are still encountered today. In Albanian folk, literature is Asllan-a name, *Babai*-“father”,
275 *bafti-a*/ “luck”, *bojë-a* /”color, ink”, *çift*-“in couple”, *damar*-“a vein, blood vessel”, *dynja* –
276 “world”, *fital*-“wicker”, *hesap*-“to account”, *hiç*-“nothing”, *Sokak*-“street”, *sheqer*-“a sugar”,
277 *shejtani*-“satan, demon”; *teneqe*-“tin, xhep-pocket”. (Gjevori, 1968, pp. 25-412).

278 Foreign words considered as Albanian property are *bastis*-to raid, to search, making control,
279 *kavga*-quarrel, fight, *inat*-anger, *ezmer/e*-swarthy person, brunette, *izën*-permission, which are
280 actually from Turkish. (Xhuvani, 1968, p. 268).

281 Turkish borrowings in Ismail Kadare's "Castles" novel. (Kadare, 2003) are as follows: Allah-
282 God, Aman-Please, Arab-inhabitant of Arabia, *Bakır*-“Copper”, *Beden*-“crenellation”,
283 “stronghold wall”, *Bismillah*-“Bismilah, a praying word”.

284 After the Renaissance period, the penetration of foreign words in the Albanian language is
285 noticed, mainly from Italian and French.

286 Italian borrowings have started to penetrate into the Albanian language since the 10th century.
287 They have been more frequent in the last two centuries and belong to the field of navigation,

288 technique, science, art. E.g.: *Muzikë*- “music”, *soprano*- “in soprano”, *kanto*- “canto”, *kimi*-
289 “chemistry”, *vapor*- “steamer”.

290 French borrowing is newer and fewer in number. They have entered mainly through written
291 language and educated people. E.g.: *bluzë*- “blouse”, *byro*- “bureau”, *garderobë*- “wardrobe”,
292 *komplet*- “complete”, *natyrë*- “nature”. (Naser Pajaziti, 2019, p. 156).

293 3. *Turkish words replaced with European words*

294

295 *Xhade*-*asfalt* / “Asphalt road”

296 *Akraba*-*familjar* / **relative**

297 *Aferim*-*bravo*, alb. *të lumtë* / “congratulation”

298 *Mutfak*-*kuzhinë* / “kitchen”

299 *Akçi*-*kuzhinier* / “chef”

300 *Tamam*, alb. *Taman*, *birinxhi-ok* / “Exactly”

301 *Taze*-*fresh* / “Fresh”

302 *Badihava*-“free” / *fri* alb.

303 *Bela*-*problem* / “problem”

304 *Xhenet*-*parajsa* / “paradise”

305 *Vilispicë*-*biçikletë* / “bicycle”

306 *Xherah*-*kirurg* / “Surgeon”

307 *Çadër*-*ombrella* / “umbrella”

308 *Damar*-*vena* / “Veins”

309 *Hendek*-*barrierë*, *bllokadë* / *Gap*-“barrier, blockade”

310 *Divan*-*hane*-*korridor* / “corridor”

311 *Gurbet*-*mërgim*, *kurbet* alb. / “Exile”

312 *Heqim*-*doktor*, alb. *Mjek* / “Doctor”

313 *Hamamxhik*-*banje*, *tualet* / “bath, toilet”

314 *Hallk*, *milet*-*popull* / “people”

315 *Hisenik*-*ortak* / “partner”

316 *Insan*-*person* / “person”

317 *Kadi*, *qatip*-*sekretar* / “secretary”

- 318 *Kapllan–tigër* / “tiger”
 319 *Meleqe–engjell* / “angel”
 320 *Myshteri–klient* / “client-customer”
 321 *Pembe–ngjyrë rozë* / “pink”
 322 *Shaka–humor* / “humor”
 323 *Zijaret–vizitë, zialet alb.* / “Visit”
 324 *Zabit–oficer* / “officer”
 325 *Havaja–klima* / “climate”
 326 *Braktis–abandonoj* / “Abandoned”
 327 *Furça–brusha* / “Brushes”
 328 *Mavi–blu* / “blue”
 329 *Hyzmeqar–shërbyes* / “servant”
 330 4. *Turkish words that have been replaced with Albanian*

- 331 *Bardak-gota* / “cups”
 332 *Penxhere-dritarja* / “window”
 333 *Kapia-dera e hyrjes* / “Entrance door”
 334 *Sahat-ora* / “Clock”
 335 *Myhyr-unazë* / “ring”
 336 *Gjyzlykë–syzet* / “glasses”
 337 *Gjerdan–qafore* / “necklace”
 338 *Bakall-shtambë* / “Grocery-pitcher”
 339 *Kundra–këpucë* / “shoes”

340 The words that are irreplaceable: *dysheme*-“floor”, *çati*-“roof”, *tavan*-“ceiling”, *beqar*-“single”,
 341 *tepsi*-“pan”, *xhezve*-“pots”, *filxhan*-“cup”, *tenxhere*-“pot”, *jorgan*-“quilt”, *jastëk*-“pillow”, and
 342 *çarçaf* – “sheet”.

343

344 5. Arguments of Turkish words in the Albanian popular literature

345 -*Fenerbahçja nuk bonë sypriz* / “Fenerbahçe are not a surprise”, (Sülça, 2007)

346 *Unë shkova, mirëpo fallxhesha nuk më këqyri fallin* / “I went, but the fortune teller did not look
347 at my fortune”.

348 - *Âsht shum rahat* / “It's very comfortable”, (Sülça, 2007, f. 6-28)

349 - *Vallahi ka ardhë koha babe, për me damtue punën e Besim beut.* / “For godsake, the time has
350 come, dad to damage the work of Besim bey”.

351 ... *kam krye me zor të gjitha dredhinat e hilet* ... / ... “I barely performed all the tricks”
352 ... (Sülça, Ngatërrestarët – Dramë, 2006)

353 - *Jo nuk âsht gjynah këto që po bajmë, por âsht shumë sevap!* / “No, it's not a pity we are
354 doing, but it's very good!” (Sülça, 2006, pp. 3-31).

355 ...*minder i vjetër allaturka* / ...”Old fashioned sofa rosary”, (Sülça, Dhandri Turk–
356 Dramë, 1989)

357 - *Mbas xhumasë jam krejt i lirë* / “After Friday I am completely free” (Sülça, Në Kosovë
358 – Tregime, 2006).

359 ...*çaji më shkon cigarja edhe ma e lezetshme, akraba* / “I like tea even the most delicious
360 cigarette, Relative” (Sülça, Bisedat mbramore – Dramë, 2008).

361 6. Conclusion

362 This paper focuses on a special aspect of grammar, lexical-grammatical processes, and
363 their analysis, including the way of entry of these elements in the Albanian language, as well as
364 their structure. This paper is based on the system of Albanian grammar, as well as the adaptation
365 of foreign words to the rules of categorization in Albanian. The paper in question places special
366 emphasis on the lexical and semantic analysis of the grammatical functions of foreign words in
367 the Turkish language compared to those of the Albanian language. We have made such an
368 analysis, based on the fact that foreign words have interfered in Albanian for many years and the
369 current situation and status of their use should be analyzed. These processes, known as

370 synonyms, homonyms, and antonyms, have a very wide use even today in the Albanian
371 language.

372 It is important that foreign interrogative sentences as linguistic expressions versus words
373 in the Albanian language represent a concrete variable and for certain purposes are the richest
374 opportunity for expression.

375 Such an analysis, seen not only within the framework of the grammar, discipline but also
376 in the semantic-pragmatic one, we think is important in the interdisciplinary aspect as well, as
377 the conclusions of the approach analysis clearly define how the grammatical aspects presented
378 here provide information about periods, and unknown absences.

379 Starting from the initial knowledge and deepening to the most complicated levels of
380 linguistics, there is a methodology of explaining lexical-semantic structures and using it to
381 communicate or practice different linguistic structures in real contexts.

382 In the context of interlinguistic interaction and the transmission of the message from the
383 mother tongue to an acquired language, or vice versa, this research aims to establish in the same
384 channel the grammatical features of the two languages, looking at them from a generativist point
385 of view.

386 It is very important to make it immediately clear that this approach can be extended from
387 the synchronic to the diachronic dimension.

388 It is characterized by the tendency to give as wide as possible the facts and typical
389 structures of full and partial words. Being a work based on a comparative analysis of these
390 sentences in two languages, Turkish and Albanian, we have tried to give the similarities and
391 differences since these languages are based mainly on rich literature obtained in Turkish and
392 Albanian. Each identification and finding of distinctive features are presented through an
393 analysis of concrete examples, taken from these two languages. Also, an important goal of the
394 paper is to make all users of the language-aware of its importance through analytical analysis.
395 that has the correct acquisition of structures and proves that the knowledge of linguistic
396 structures and the act of speaking, play a fundamental role in the better mastery of the language.
397 The description and analysis of the structures, the peculiarities of their interpretation in this paper

398 aim to prove that in addition to the differences we also have in common between these two
399 languages, although two languages are far from each other. It is worth noting that the
400 commonalities are not only linguistic but also semantic. This approach would help in their use,
401 practice, and interpretation in linguistics

402 This study can never be exhaustive, as it can serve for further treatment with the object of
403 a more detailed analysis of specific aspects related to the problem of foreign sentences, and in
404 particular lexical-semantic processes.

405 7. *Acknowledgements*

406 The paper aims to inform the reader that we still have the presence of structures in both
407 languages, their features and commonalities are conductors of attitudes and emotional loads
408 according to language patterns, but also as a way of looking at the world and thinking about it in
409 words.

410 Therefore, when learning and explaining borrowings in a language, it is important to
411 provide a bridge between cultural interaction and the use of the foreign language naturally,
412 which will lead to more productive language learning and correct use.

413 This will lead to a more accurate acquisition and use of these structures for communicative
414 purposes in languages. Therefore, we found it important to use the approach method in this
415 paper, juxtaposing the structure in a foreign (Turkish) language that is in the Albanian language
416 in order, beyond the specifics of these systems, to discover their common features. The methods
417 we used in dealing with our case are based on the comparison, observation, and interpretation. It
418 is a clearer picture of the linguistic relations between spoken and written Albanian, especially in
419 the case of Albanian versus Turkish borrowings. The predominant method of research is
420 comparison and interpretation. This is because comparative language studies play a crucial role
421 in determining universal and specific features. Through these studies, it has been discovered that
422 the features through which languages differ tend to be organized into groups that are consistent
423 across languages and which allow typologies of languages. And it is precisely the parametric
424 approaches that could explain why we find certain features of borrowing in different languages.

425

426 8. *Notes*

427 In Naser Pajaziti, 2019, we can verify that Indo-European source words are more easily
428 distinguished by comparison with the corresponding words of Indo-European languages close to
429 the Albanian language.

430 In Vajzoviç, 1999 - Lexical-semantic processes are detailly prescribed, like: Polysemy is
431 a sign that has many meanings, but with the same etymology, expresses the same content;
432 Homonymy is a sign that has two meanings, with different etymologies; Synonymy represents
433 many signs with the same meaning, with the same or close semantic value and Antonyms
434 represents different signs with semantic contradictions.

435 In Hudson, 2000, we have polysemy when the form of the word suggests different
436 meanings, but all those meanings are related according to the semantic line.

437 In *Gjuha shqipe 1*, 2019; Dizdari, 2006; Hoxha, 2015; Pajaziti, 2019; Vajzoviç, 1999;
438 *Turqishtja e re*, 2007; IAP, 1989; I have collected all turkish words in standard albanian.

439 Turkish words in folk literature/dialectology of albanian are in Asllani, 1963; Çeta, 1974;
440 Gjevori, 1968; Xhuvani, 1968; Sülça, 2007; Sülça, 2006; Sülça, 2008; Sülça, 1989.

441 In Kadare, 2003, are mentioned many active turkish words in albanian language.

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